

White Paper
Task Force 2: Efficient Building Operation
Topic A :
Interoperability

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Document information

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Executive summary

The SmartBuilt4EU project has set up four task forces investigating issues related to smart buildings: their objective is to identify the remaining challenges and barriers to smart building deployment, and the associated research and innovation gaps that should be addressed in the near future.

*Task force 2 focuses on the optimal integration and use of smart solutions to allow an efficient building operation. The Task Force investigates what are the interoperability requirements to ensure a seamless operation, as well as the optimisation in terms of building costs and reduction of environmental impacts, over the full life cycle. The first topic addressed by this task force and presented in this paper is **Interoperability**.*

Smart building solutions are a strong leverage for increased energy efficiency in buildings, improved quality of life for occupants and added value for work performance. However the degree of interoperability of technical building systems (and analysis / software tools that use data from these systems) can be a limiting factor affecting the smart services and impacts that can be delivered within a building. Interoperability is essential for allowing technical building systems to interact with the energy grids, can avoid duplication of efforts and is desirable in the light of future upgrades of the building. On the downside, it can increase the risk for malfunctioning and introduce cybersecurity and liability risks.

This white paper therefore aims to provide an overview on what is known and what should be further investigated to answer the following questions:

- How to define, implement, assess and monitor interoperability in a Smart Building so it can deliver its functionalities?
- To what extent can interoperability hamper a democratic and inclusive access to technologies and services?
- How can the risks associated to cybersecurity and malfunctioning be minimised?

In its first part, this paper provides a state of the art regarding the following issues, specific attention being paid to EC-funded projects:

- Definition of interoperability: several definitions exist, and several categories of interoperability are described in the literature. This White Paper focuses on technical, syntactical and semantic interoperability of buildings systems and components, and adopts the following definition: "Interoperability is the ability of two or more systems or components to exchange data and use information"
- Standards, data exchanges protocols and ontologies: an overview of the IoT standards, protocols and ontology landscape is provided.
- Hardware solutions for the integration of legacy systems and domestic appliances (e.g. wired and wireless sensors and actuators)
- Interoperability assessment: Assessing the different levels of interoperability of a building is a challenge. Whilst interoperability is acknowledged as a very important concern in relation to the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI), there are significant limitations to the actionability of the explicit evaluation of the interoperability. The way interoperability is taken into account by other existing smart certifications also varies greatly from one certification to the other.

A brainstorming process then enabled to identify some key barriers and drivers regarding the interoperability of smart building components and systems. The next diagrams provide an overview of the main barriers and drivers discussed.

VALUE CHAIN	Vendor Lock-in (e.g. in the case of solutions sold with support & maintenance)	Top barriers according to the Task Force
	Readiness of industrial players and complexity of value chain	
REGULATION	Lack of industrial standards for homogenous interoperability	
	Data integration issues related to GDPR	
	Lack of regulation preventing or discouraging vendor lock-in	
SOCIAL	User acceptance / Final users' awareness and user friendliness	
	Complex inclusiveness, lack of human-centric solutions for non-expert users	
ECONOMIC	Reluctancy to adopt interoperability by manufacturers as it might affect market share / profit	
	Reluctancy to adopt interoperability by service providers / integrators who generate a lot of business on tailor made integrations	
	Cost related to IoT investment or semantic modelling (i.e. BIM)	
TECHNICAL	Cybersecurity of open systems	
	Low "Smartness" of the building stock/ legacy equipment	

Figure 1: Overview of main barriers

VALUE CHAIN	Market push	Top drivers according to the Task Force
	Initiatives from market actors providing energy and non-energy services	
	Democratisation of data assets/ strong push to make all the data available to all market players in the value chain	
REGULATION & STANDARDS	EU Regulation: EPBD, SRI, DIGITAL LOGBOOK and RENOVATION PASSPORT	
	Renovation Wave	
	(Open) standards	
SOCIAL	New trends in health care (tele-assistance)	
	Customers requesting more plug-&-play solutions, democratisation of smart devices	
	Buildings becoming active in energy market: occupants require interoperability	
	Inclusiveness: a building should be as simple as a smart phone	
ECONOMIC	Reduced development costs for new services thanks to interoperability	
TECHNICAL	Cybersecurity: push to have a more interoperable system providing increased shared resistance to cyberattacks	
	Enhancement of potential synergies among devices	
	Crowd-evaluation of protocols	

Figure 2: Overview of main drivers

Based on the State of the Art and the barriers and drivers, a number of research and innovation gaps were identified. They are synthetised in the next diagrams (the framed ones are those that were identified as priorities in the last meeting with the Task Force members). The topics of data ownership and privacy as well as cyber security will be further investigated in the Topic B of the 4th Task Force.

Figure 3: R&I gaps

Figure 4: “Go-to-market’ gaps

The ‘gaps’ identified above will feed the elaboration of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda on smart buildings that will be produced by the SmartBuilt4EU consortium by mid-2023, together with some recommendations targeting policy makers.

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List of abbreviations

A&P	Adapt-&-Play
AIOTI	Alliance for the Internet of Things Innovation
API	Application Programming Interface
BAC	Building Automation and Control
BEMS	Building Energy Management Systems
BIM	and Building Information Modelling
BMS	Building Management Systems
DR	Demand Response
DSO	Distribution System Operator
DT	Digital Twins
EC	European Commission
EEB	Energy Efficient Building
EMS	Energy Management Systems
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
eVs	Electric Vehicles
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
GWAC	GridWise Architecture Council
HVAC	Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes
IoT	Internet of Things
R2S	Ready2Service
SAREF	Smart Appliances REference
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
TBS	Technical Building System
TF	Task Force

1. Introduction

This white paper is produced in the context of the SmartBuilt4EU project, a coordination and support action funded by the European Commission to bring together the research and innovation community on smart buildings.

The SmartBuilt4EU project has set up four task forces investigating topics related to smart buildings. They respectively address the interaction between building and end-user, efficient building operation, interactions between the building and the external environment, and cross cutting issues.

Figure 5: The four Task Forces set up by the SmartBuilt4EU project

SmartBuilt4EU Task Force 2 focuses on the optimal integration and use of smart solutions to allow an efficient building operation. The Task Force investigates what are the interoperability requirements to ensure a seamless operation, as well as the optimisation in terms of building costs and reduction of environmental impacts, over the full life cycle.

The Task Force will focus on 3 topics (one per semester):

1. **Interoperability:** Interoperability among building components & systems
2. **Optimised building costs:** Integrating tools for optimised costs over the full life cycle (incl. BIM, digital twin, predictive maintenance, Artificial Intelligence, weather forecast, predictive control)
3. **Smartness to reduce building's environmental impacts:** Integrating tools to reduce the environmental impact over the full life cycle, paying attention to the carbon footprint of smart solutions (incl. Resource efficiency, Environmental impact management, Integration of renewable energies)

The present White Paper focusses on the first topic, i.e. "Interoperability" and presents the outcomes of a collective work, carried out with the members of the Task Forces, in several steps:

- Agreement on the scope
- Review of the State of the Art and identification of the points to be investigated in particular
- Analysis of barriers and drivers
- Identification of R&I gaps
- Key conclusions on the topics and recommendations

2. Topic under investigation by the Task Force

2.1. Rationale

Interoperability in smart buildings refers to several fields, namely energy management, smart appliances, comfort and lighting, control and connectivity, security.

Smart building is currently an incredibly fruitful market sector. According to Statista¹, the smart homes world market² is expected to show an annual growth rate of 15.64% between 2020 and 2025 (with a forecasted worldwide market size of 99.51bn USD in 2021). In 2020, almost 225 million households worldwide were considered “smart” and this number is expected to amount to 478 million by 2025.

In the literature, most contributions about Smart Buildings tend to focus on IoT technologies (Feldmeier and Paradiso, 2010; Sung et al., 2019; Salamone et al., 2018) or on energy simulation and grid management (Ashrafian et al., 2019; Nouvel and Alessi, 2012; Pellegrino et al., 2016). In other works, more complex systems are conceived, combining IoT architectures with building simulation (Zhao et al., 2016; Escandón et al., 2019; Ramallo-González et al., 2019) or with energy flexibility (Pombeiro et al., 2017; Cetin et al., 2019). Nevertheless, these studies mostly do not consider the user behaviour. Recent studies show growing attention to the people’s control and responsibility. According to several studies (Dell’Isola et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2020), users tend to adopt a pro-environmental attitude when they are included in the loop and are conscious of the energetic problem. For instance, the combined use of a Building Management System, energy simulation and participatory sensing through a mobile app gave incredibly good results in terms of energy savings (Zangheri et al, 2019, Tomat et al, 2020).

The degree of interoperability of technical building systems (and analysis / software tools that use data from these systems) can be a limiting factor affecting the smart services and impacts that can be delivered within a building. Interoperability of systems can avoid duplication of efforts (e.g. investment for occupancy detection systems and monitoring displays for lighting, for space heating and cooling and ventilation systems) and optimise the control and maintenance of technical building systems (e.g. single interface for controlling heating and cooling facilitates the operation of the building and prevents spilling energy through uncoordinated simultaneous heating and cooling in building zones). Furthermore, interoperability is essential for allowing technical building systems to interact with the energy grids. Finally, interoperable systems are desirable in the light of future upgrades of the building as they can avoid proprietary lock-in and facilitate innovative solutions.

There can, however, also be a downside to interoperability. Exploiting interoperability through connecting various systems – potentially stemming from multiple manufacturers – can increase the risk for malfunctioning compared to proprietary systems and protocols. Fault diagnosis in a system of interconnected technical building systems can also be more intricate compared to a set of stand-alone systems. Finally, the delineation of responsibility for the provision of the service can become blurred in case of interoperable and interconnected systems. This can introduce cybersecurity risks and the risk that an end user is unable to establish who is responsible for the service and hence cannot legally seek recourse if a service they have paid for is not functioning as intended.

¹ <https://www.statista.com/topics/2430/smart-homes/> and <https://www.statista.com/forecasts/887613/number-of-smart-homes-in-the-smart-home-market-in-the-world>

² The Smart Home market constitutes the sale of networked devices and related services that enable home automation for private end users (B2C)

This white paper therefore aims to provide an overview on what is known and what should be further investigated to answer the following questions:

- How to define, implement, assess and monitor interoperability in a Smart Building so it can deliver its functionalities?
- To what extent can interoperability hamper a democratic and inclusive access to technologies and services?
- How can the risks associated to cybersecurity and malfunctioning be minimised?

2.2. Scope

The following ‘blocks of knowledge’ were identified during the 1st meeting of the Task Force:

- Definitions and levels of interoperability (and how to assess it);
- Standardisation, protocols, ontologies;
- Solutions to support interoperability;
- Data sharing and data security.

Figure 6: Blocks of knowledge identified

Definitions and levels of interoperability

There are multiple definitions of interoperability (by e.g. ETSI, ISO). Also, different levels of interoperability have also been defined³. They include for instance:

- technical interoperability (Systems and components that should work seamlessly together: sensors, actuators, central controllers and displays, etc.);
- syntactical interoperability;
- semantic interoperability.

Interoperability can also be cross-domain, be local or global.

³ see [white paper](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/336677616_Towards_Semantic_Interoperability_Standards_based_on_Ontologies?channel=doi&linkId=5dac45da4585155e27f7614f&showFulltext=true) : https://www.researchgate.net/publication/336677616_Towards_Semantic_Interoperability_Standards_based_on_Ontologies?channel=doi&linkId=5dac45da4585155e27f7614f&showFulltext=true

In contrast, its **assessment** as a building owner or assessor (in the framework of SRI for instance), and the way to communicate around it, is not yet extensively defined.

Standardisation, protocols, ontologies

Several open and standard data models exist today (e.g. IFC, SAREF...). Having a standard physical layer may prove difficult when legacy equipment⁴ is involved: a way forward is therefore to have a common/ unified ontology for technical components. Open API definitions and open (and linked) datasets (e.g. Building Information Modelling (BIM) vs sensors vs energy systems) are another important topic.

Solutions to support interoperability

Different initiatives already exist or are being developed to support interoperability:

- Building Operating System to consolidate data sets from assets;
- Communication protocols and gateways, communication drivers for sensors, actuators, appliances...;
- OpenBIM extends the benefits of BIM by improving the accessibility, usability, management and sustainability of digital data in the built asset industry⁵;
- Open Commissioning Tools;
- IFC - IoT for digital twins deployment on buildings;
- Demand response technologies, which request a high degree of interoperability⁶.

The respective roles of the different Smart Buildings stakeholders remain however unclear, e.g. who should do what in creating and enabling open workflow capabilities?

Data Sharing and Data Security

- Data Processing and Data ownership topics associated to data from technical and IoT devices
- Extra cyber-security risks

This will be addressed by the topic on Data Governance by the Task Force working on Cross-cutting issues.

The scope of the “Interoperability” topic to be investigated by this Task Force is synthesised as follows:

- Definition of interoperability: what is meant by interoperability in Smart Buildings? (*different types, different scales*)
- What are the requirements when designing, deploying and using Smart Buildings tools, technologies and equipment? (*standards, communication and data exchange protocols, etc.*)
- How is interoperability evaluated in smart building certifications?
- What are the respective roles of the different Smart Buildings stakeholders? (*from manufacturers to building owners*)

⁴ i.e. equipment already in place, some of which may be obsolete or no longer in production, and to which a new system should connect (sometimes with difficulties to integrate)

⁵ <https://www.buildingsmart.org/about/openbim/openbim-definition/>

⁶ see also TF3/ topic A on Grid integration

3. State of the Art

3.1. Definition of interoperability

Following definitions of the word interoperability are currently in place:

- **ISO/IEC 2382-01**⁷: *“The capability to communicate, execute programs, or transfer data among various functional units in a manner that requires the user to have little or no knowledge of the unique characteristics of those units”*
- **ETSI**⁸: *“Interoperability can be considered to be the ability of two or more systems or components to exchange data and use information”*
- Interoperability is defined in the **European Interoperability Framework (EIF)**⁹ as *“the ability of organisations to interact towards mutually beneficial goals, involving the sharing of information and knowledge between these organisations, through the business processes they support, by means of the exchange of data between their ICT systems.”*

Different categories of interoperability are also described by ETSI in their White Paper n°3 (ETSI, 2008):

- **Technical Interoperability** is usually associated with hardware/software components, systems and platforms that enable machine-to-machine communication to take place. This kind of interoperability is often centred on (communication) protocols and the infrastructure needed for those protocols to operate.
- **Syntactical Interoperability** is usually associated with data formats. Certainly, the messages transferred by communication protocols need to have a well-defined syntax and encoding, even if it is only in the form of bit-tables. However, many protocols carry data or content, and this can be represented using high-level transfer syntaxes such as HTML, XML or ASN.1.
- **Semantic Interoperability** is usually associated with the meaning of content and concerns the human rather than machine interpretation of the content. Thus, interoperability on this level means that there is a common understanding between people of the meaning of the content (information) being exchanged.
- **Organisational Interoperability**, as the name implies, is the ability of organizations to effectively communicate and transfer (meaningful) data (information) even though they may be using a variety of different information systems over widely different infrastructures, possibly across different geographic regions and cultures. Organizational interoperability depends on successful technical, syntactical and semantic interoperability.

GridWise® Architecture Council (GWAC) provides a slightly different interoperability stack (Figure 7).

⁷ ISO/IEC 2382:2015 “Information technology — Vocabulary” see <https://www.iso.org/standard/63598.html>

⁸ ETSI (2008) ETSI White Paper No. 3 - Achieving Technical Interoperability - the ETSI Approach

⁹ part of the Communication (COM(2017)134) from the European Commission adopted on 23 March 2017, see https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/eif_en

Figure 7: GWAC interoperability stack

“User centred interoperability” (i.e. development of plug and play modular IoT, scalable decentralized infrastructure, multi-stakeholders services, visualization of information and global real life cycle performance assessment) is also gaining traction, but is not in the scope of this White Paper.

This white paper covers the first three categories described by ETSI (technical, syntactical, semantic). The following definition of interoperability will be used from now on: **“Interoperability is the ability of two or more systems or components to exchange data and use information”**.

3.2. Literature review

3.2.1. Standards, data exchange protocols and ontologies

The widespread adoption of smart EEB solutions is currently being hampered by the limited interoperability and data exchange between the ICT components. Building management systems (BMSs) have evolved in recent years to support and efficiently operate diverse systems and appliances through technologies and ICT solutions; however, comprehensive multi-system management using one all-inclusive BMS (in a manager-of-managers role) and standardization of data flows, data analysis, and actuation remains an unattained goal (Minoli et al, 2017). Semantic Web technologies are geared towards providing data interoperability, where semantic labels are used to described entities, their properties and links among them. Within the Semantic Web, ontologies can be used to describe more complex and formal collections of domain-specific terms and relationships. Different building ontologies have been suggested in the literature, such as BOT¹⁰, Brick¹¹, ifcOWL¹², and SAREF4BLDG¹³. While there is an agreement on the benefits of semantic annotations, the annotation process itself still relies heavily on (manually) writing semantic mappings to the different types of devices. While some ontologies are accompanied by tools for mapping buildings’ data to their model (Fierro

¹⁰ W3C BOT: <https://w3c-lbd-cg.github.io/bot>

¹¹ Brick Shema. <https://brickschema.org/>

¹² IFCOWL. <https://github.com/buildingSMART/ifcOWL>

¹³ SAREF. <https://w3id.org/def/saref4bldg>

et al, 2018), an automated process for semantic annotation, based on data analysis to determine which set of labels best describes the data, is still missing.

An overview of the IoT standards and protocols landscape is provided by **AIOTI WG03**, 2019 (although more at the technical and syntactical level) – see Figure 8. The most relevant vertical domains have been framed in red.

Figure 8: IoT standards development organisations (SDOs) and alliances landscape (Vertical and Horizontal Domains)

Concerning a similar landscape, but on ontologies (therefore interoperability at the semantic level), AIOTI WG03 is also creating an ontology landscape - see Figure 9 (first version of the document to be released S2 2021).

Figure 9: IoT ontology landscape (source: AIOTI WG03, 2021, publication pending)

A European Commission study (SMART 2016/0082, 2018) on Digitalising the energy sector: "Ensuring interoperability for enabling Demand Side Flexibility" | Shaping Europe’s digital future contains a state of standardization (Section 3) for the energy domain. Another (older) study (SMART 2013/0077, 2015) provides an overview of semantic assets for smart appliances interoperability and a state of standardization for BIM, Energy and IoT.

Based on an exercise of listing the different standards and protocols with a focus on interoperability 1) during the construction phase / BIM related, and 2) within a building during operation, a non-exhaustive list is presented in Table 1. A similar list on semantic taxonomies and ontologies is presented in Table 2.

Table 1: Standards and protocols listed by the Task Force members, with a focus on interoperability

Type of standard	Examples of standards/ protocols	Short description
Construction phase & BIM		
Syntax standards	XML, JSON, SPFF, OWL, RDF, JSON-LD	Open
Encoding Standards	CityGML Product Templates Building Smart Dictionary	Data (e.g. Data Dictionary)
		Open data model and XML-based format for the storage and exchange of virtual 3D city models. It is an application scheme for the Geography Markup Language version 3.1.1 (GML3), the extendible international standard for spatial data exchange issued by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) and the ISO TC211. The aim of the development of CityGML is to reach a common definition of the basic entities, attributes, and relations of a 3D city model. This is especially important with respect to the cost-effective sustainable maintenance of 3D city models, allowing the reuse of the same data in different application fields. CityGML OGC
Operation phase (for Building Automation and Control - BAC)		
IoT communication protocols¹⁴	BACnet	BACnet is a communication protocol for BAC networks that leverage the ASHRAE, ANSI, and ISO 16484-5 standard protocol.
	LoraWan	Open. Slow data rate, high range and low battery consumption
	Wi-Fi	High data rate, high range and high power consumption (requires mains power)
	Zigbee	Open. Slow data rate, medium range and very low battery consumption
	Li-Fi	Wireless communication technology which utilizes light to transmit data and position between device
	KNX	KNX is an open standard (see EN 50090, ISO/IEC 14543) for commercial and domestic building automation. KNX devices can manage lighting, blinds and shutters, HVAC, security systems, energy management, audio video, white goods,

¹⁴ Please note that this category includes IoT protocols as well as telecom protocols and wireless technologies

		displays, remote control, etc. Can use several physical communication media (wired and radio)
		Other protocols include: Bluetooth, Modbus, DACI, EnOcean, LonWorks, LonMark, oBIX, OPC, Sigfox, Z-Wave, MQTT, CoAP, REST
API specifications	NGSI-LD, REST, OpenCDE API, BCF API	Open

Table 2: Semantic taxonomies and ontologies

Construction phase & BIM	
Industry Foundation Classes (IFC)	ISO 16739:2013 represents an open international standard for BIM data that is exchanged and shared among software applications used by the various participants in a building construction or facility management project. The desired IFC data can be encoded in various formats, such as XML, JSON, and STEP
BIM Collaboration Format (BCF)	ISO 29481-1:2016 is intended to facilitate interoperability between software applications used during all stages of the life cycle of construction works, including briefing, design, documentation, construction, operation and maintenance, and demolition. It promotes digital collaboration between actors in the construction process and provides a basis for accurate, reliable, repeatable and high-quality information exchange.
ISO 6707: Buildings and civil engineering works — Vocabulary — Part 1: General terms	ISO 6707 contains the terms and definitions of general concepts to establish a vocabulary applicable to buildings and civil engineering works: a) fundamental concepts, which can be the starting point for other, more specific, definitions; b) more specific concepts, used in several areas of construction and frequently used in standards, regulations and contracts.
Ontology for Property Management (OPM)	Specifically focused on managing construction project properties and their evolution over time (traceability in time). The idea is to change a "state" of a property and keep a record of modifications.
RealEstateCore	A practical way to represent "things" in a building, with some basic spatial abstracts for a building. These are used to monitor devices within a building with the intention to describe their connections. There is ongoing work on upscaling this to the "smart cities" level. The full ontology consists of 7 modules. The ontologies include many individuals to represent units of measurement and other things.
ifcOWL	IFC semantic data standard expressed in the open syntax OWL
BOT	A specific ontology for describing building spatial components, from spaces to zones, as well as the connections and "interfaces" between these. Can be used to deduce if two zones or spaces are touching for example. Well aligned with IfcOwl, but much smaller.
CoClass	CoClass is a Swedish classification system for the built environment.

Omniclass	The OmniClass Construction Classification System (usually referred to as OmniClass™ or OCCS) is a classification system for the construction industry in North America. It follows the international framework set out in ISO 12006-2
Uniclass	Uniclass 2015 is a unified classification for the UK industry covering all construction sectors.
Operation phase	
Brick	The BRICK ontology is a description of how to classify "things" as classes, similar in function to SKOS/XKOS on adding specificity to instances. Rather than adding symbols (such as classification codes), the BRICK schema was made to deduce the specific class based on "tags" and "tagsets". Thus, the classes of an individual/instance can be deduced from these tags using reasoning. The BRICK rdf graph has to be generated from the python code.
SAREF FIWARE smart data models	An ontology (unified data model for appliances) that makes it possible for any home appliance to talk to any energy management system thus enabling the smart home.
Interaction with the grid (see also Task Force 3)	
OpenADR	A non-proprietary, open standardized DR interface that allows electricity providers to communicate DR signals directly to existing customers using a common language and existing communications such as the Internet.
IEC 61970/61968 CIM	An ontology model that allows the exchange of information regarding the electric grid among different software applications.
Universal Smart Energy Framework (USEF)	A framework describing the market for flexibility, enabling commoditization and market trading of flexible energy use. Specifies all stakeholder roles and how they interact.

3.2.2. Hardware solutions for the integration of legacy systems and domestic appliances

An important enabling factor for IoT adoption in existing buildings is the integration of several technologies and communications solutions (Brous et al, 2019). Some of the technological solutions involve wired and wireless sensor and actuator networks, which play a central role of connecting machines, parts, products, and humans and create a diverse set of new applications to support intelligent and autonomous decision making (Raza et al, 2019). The optimal automation of all systems within the building requires the collection of data, which implies that various types of sensors need to be installed in the building to collect these data. Moreover, most of the legacy systems already installed in existing buildings need to be upgraded with wired or wireless actuators, which allow the automatic operation of them. Finally, to connect all this equipment and to connect the building with other parties, diverse communication technologies need to be used. For instance, heterogeneous wireless technologies, such as WiFi or cellular (3G, 4G, and future 5G (European Commission, 2019)) can be used for the communication system. Due to complementary characteristics of such networks, more connectivity opportunities are available. All these technologies may allow increasing the connectivity and automated operation of legacy systems and appliances, which is the first step to increase their smartness.

Lam and Wang (2013) proposed a platform that connects the Building Management System (BMS) to a smartphone app, called CarryEn, to improve energy savings and connectivity among the different elements

of the Smart Building. The app aims to find the optimised set-point according to both the thermal preferences voted by the users and data collected from the BMS. After two experiments, one in a commercial building and one in the campus of their university, an optimising algorithm was obtained and 13% of energy-saving was achieved. **In this case, it is important to notice how a good result in terms of smartness and sustainability is achieved through interoperability.** Furthermore, including the connection with the smartphone app, this platform enables the users to make use the potential of the entire system.

Pritoni et al. (2017), implemented a Wi-Fi system that connected thermostats with rooftop units to collect outdoor air temperature. They analysed three different thermostat strategies: one based on a constant set-point schedule, a second strategy based on the users' thermal comfort vote and a third strategy considering both users' vote and outdoor air temperature in order to achieve energy-efficiency aims. The third method resulted to be most effective, since it was possible to save up to 20%–30% of energy use without compromising comfort.

Li et al. (2017) proposed a complete architecture that acquired both environmental data and human physiological and behavioural data in order to develop a personalised HVAC control framework. The system collects physical data through room sensors. Instead, the human data, both behavioural and physiological, were obtained through wearable devices. Through a decision algorithm developed in Python, the set-point of the HVAC system was dynamically changed. The experiment presented two case studies, one in an office building and one in a residential building. They concluded that the algorithm could reduce the uncomfortable reports by 53.7% and they demonstrated an 80% accuracy of the method in predicting thermal preference, which is a key factor for the design of energy flexibility in smart buildings.

The gap up to now lays in the fact that energy demand reduction and energy saving are indeed achieved by the interoperability in the smart buildings, but a holistic vision in which all these separate efforts are unified under a precise goal at the grid level is still missing.

3.2.3. Interoperability assessment

Assessing the different levels of interoperability of a building is a challenge. While technical interoperability can be already assessed and certified, semantic interoperability is still difficult to assess and certify, especially when using ontologies, which are quite an abstract concept.

The following section therefore focusses on assessing the technical operability.

Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI)

In the SRI methodology, the smart readiness of a building or building unit is determined based on the assessment of smart ready services (and their functionality level) present in a building. As such, it reflects the capabilities of the building or building unit to adapt its operation to the needs of the occupants and the grid, and to improve its energy efficiency and overall performance. Apart from these key capabilities, there are some cross-cutting issues related to the greater uptake of smart technologies, including interoperability of the technical buildings systems. The SRI could potentially play a role in informing the market actors on this important aspect and even assist in shaping the market.

A formal evaluation of interoperability which affects the SRI scoring process is not feasible. Whilst interoperability is acknowledged as a very important concern in relation to the SRI, there are significant limitations to the actionability of the explicit evaluation of the interoperability. This would require in-depth information on a very broad range of technologies and implementation routes by numerous vendors. This

information is usually not readily available to an assessor and would require additional investigations. Especially in the case of legacy equipment it might be very hard or even impossible to retrieve sufficiently detailed information. Furthermore, such an assessment would need to be performed for many of the technical building systems present in a building (heating, cooling, lighting, ventilation, BMS...), requiring a large amount of time and effort which would have important repercussions on the cost of an SRI assessment. Furthermore, the SRI would in any case only provide a snapshot of the current status of the interoperability features of the technical building systems. This is a fast-moving field, and many software and hardware solutions emerge which allow interoperability despite using different technologies and protocols, for example a DALI-to-KNX gateway to integrate lighting and KNX control. Finally, this approach would require further efforts to generate a broad consensus on standards and protocols that would be accepted or the development of other definitions and a calculation method to explicitly rate interoperability scores. Due to the lack of definitions and standardization and the intricacy of an on-site assessment process covering a very wide range of products and technologies, the explicit evaluation of interoperability as part of the SRI calculation methodology is not preferred.

Instead, interoperability is included in a blended approach, combining an implicit approach and a voluntary inclusion of information provision on interoperability aspects:

- **Implicit approach:** Define services that require interoperability, without defining the required standards or protocols needed to enable such interoperability. For example, if a service for "avoiding simultaneous heating and cooling" is present, implicitly these systems will inherently have to be interoperable (either directly or through other gateways).
- **Informative approach:** Provide information on the level of interoperability of services (based on the standards and protocols featured by a given TBS), for instance, in the SRI and accompanying documents. A structured overview of such information provides a valuable source for building owners when planning to upgrade their building systems.

In other smart certifications

Several certifications and labels exist for smart buildings. The way they take interoperability into account varies greatly from one certification to the other, as presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Interoperability in smart certifications

Name of certification	Short description
<u>WiredScore</u>	Global digital connectivity rating scheme (for offices and homes). Interoperability is not specifically mentioned.
<u>SmartScore</u>	SmartScore scores the breadth and depth of the smart user stories (i.e. user functionality) implemented as well as assessing the technology, processes and procedures that support their implementation. This includes the evaluation of the range of building systems and their integration via software platforms, the evaluation of the wired and wireless infrastructure implemented for building systems along with the capacity and range of protocols supported, and data gathering and sharing.
<u>Ready2Service</u>	French label based on a reference framework that sets out the requirements to be met by a Smart Building, an open and communicating building, ready for the services. R2S includes a theme "Equipment and interfaces", which deals with APIs (i.e. presence or absence of documented API, scope, modalities for data access, etc.)

3.2.4. Interoperability and cybersecurity

As building management systems become more tightly integrated with each other and also integrated with systems outside the building (like the smart grid), they become more vulnerable to attacks that could disrupt building operations and create safety risks. This critical topic will be investigated by Task Force 4 on Cross-cutting issues in its topic on Data privacy, security and governance.

3.3. Lessons learnt from Horizon 2020 projects

3.3.1. Overview

Many H2020 projects have reviewed, developed and/or demonstrated new business model: some of them are pictured in Figure 10. Although it is likely that this list is not exhaustive, it covers the projects represented (or mentioned) in the Task Force.

Figure 10: Relevant H2020 projects identified by the Task Force members

Key lessons learnt or conclusions from some of these projects have already been presented in the state of the art. Lessons learnt from recent projects HOLISDER, TABEDE and PHOENIX are presented below.

3.3.2. Lessons learnt from the HOLISDER project

HOLISDER (completed in March 2021) brought together a wide range of mature technologies and integrated them in an open and interoperable framework, comprising in a fully-fledged suite of tools addressing the needs of the whole demand response value chain. The objective was to ensure consumer empowerment and

transformation into active market players, through the deployment of a variety of implicit and hybrid demand response schemes, supported by a variety of end-user applications for personalized informative billing, human-centric energy management, load scheduling and intelligent controls, self-consumption promotion and cost-effective storage, predictive maintenance, along with context-aware automation.

Main conclusions:

The integration of demand response enabling elements into EMS towards optimizing, at building level, energy consumption, production and storage considering the availability and price of energy supplied via the grid is a challenge. A specific challenge is that EMS and smart home devices are often not interoperable but are linked to a certain brand, technology and/or standard. Full interoperability between grids, systems and products for seamless integration of all required components in building energy management systems is crucial. Also, sub-sequent penetration of demand response in energy markets heavily relies on the deep and comprehensive understanding of real-life complexities imposed during actual operation, as well as on the smooth end-to-end interoperable communication between all actors involved. Both these parameters span four interrelated areas: physical systems (buildings, their equipment and their usage, along with districts and energy networks), human systems (occupants and their behaviours), energy markets (energy tariffs, transaction requirements and access of small consumers) and the general surrounding environment (weather fluctuations and impact on the other systems). The inadequacy of current technical offerings, business practices, market structures and regulatory frameworks to effectively address and smoothly integrate all these interrelated domains is the root cause for the slow pace of demand response introduction in energy markets and the failure to empower consumers towards becoming more active energy market actors.

There remain several key enablers that need to be satisfied towards unleashing the huge potential and enhancing the commercial viability of demand side flexibility offered by the building sector, while maximizing its value for both prosumers and energy market stakeholders. One of the main key enablers is the **establishment of end-to-end interoperability** between energy networks, building energy management systems and devices: Smart technologies for grids and buildings need to be widely deployed, highly replicable and easy to install and use. They need to simplify the interaction of consumers with energy markets, by tackling technical barriers and enabling standards-based two-way communication, plug-and-play installation and data exchange and integration across brands and protocols. Intelligent energy management systems need to be deployed offering sophisticated features for human-centric control and automation in a holistic optimization framework that considers energy prices (elasticity of consumers), demand profiles and consumer preferences (comfort, indoor environment quality contributing to the definition of flexibility profiles), local generation and storage capacity. **Compliance with open standards is therefore required to ensure end-to-end semantic and technical interoperability**, while enabling integration of Demand Response Management Systems, with Building Energy Management Systems and Smart Home components and facilitating communication between the different actors involved in the energy market. Special attention shall also be given to data protection, security and privacy. An important part of value in the future energy market will stem from large data flows and the wider integration of information and communication technology into energy management systems. Therefore, direct access to metering and consumer data needs to be ensured towards the consumer but also any third party designated to act on behalf of the consumer. Moreover, clear rules and mechanisms for the protection of consumer data and cybersecurity need to be put in place to enhance malicious events or mistreatment of such sensitive information.

Key lessons learnt relevant to interoperability include:

- Expand interoperability and consolidate security from the system operator to the smart device level
- The development of brand-agnostic services is complicated by the multitude of in-house and "walled garden" approach of some of the equipment manufacturers.

- Semantic interoperability is required at all levels; however, the landscape is still fragmented.
- Data minimisation and clear security standards are key to ensure data security and privacy.

3.3.3. Lessons learnt from the TABEDE project

TABEDE (completed in April 2021) aimed to allow all buildings equipped with Building Management Systems (BMS) to integrate energy grid demand response (DR) schemes, independently of communication protocols. The overarching objectives were to develop a highly interoperable system that maximizes building flexibility with energy cost savings validated in real buildings.

Lessons learnt include recommendations for standardization bodies:

- Harmonise the implementation of standards
- Create interoperability testing networks
- Establish a common standard to govern DR communication between the grid and buildings

3.3.4. Lessons learnt from the PHOENIX project

PHOENIX aims to use Adapt-&Play (A&P) solutions to seamlessly integrate legacy equipment, smart appliances, smart controls and technology building systems. These A&P solutions will allow the use of smart operation strategies for the upgraded equipment that should increase the satisfaction, health and well-being of all building’s occupants. Furthermore, those upgraded appliances should allow the automatic realisation of demand response actions sent by aggregators or DSOs.

(see detailed description in section 9)

Lessons learnt so far:

The main success that PHOENIX has achieved so far is through the usage of semantics as a basis of interoperability: this has been on several different levels, but has focused on the communication across APIs (not data file formats):

- Providing mappings between known endpoints and the APIs used at each of the endpoints, so that a software tool that supports multiple APIs can know which API to utilise.
- Providing some aspects of modelling of individual APIs to allow software tools to construct requests from the information modelling in an ontology.
- When APIs provide a semantic query endpoint being able to construct queries based on the query language required and the semantics modelled within the ontology.

3.4. Other initiatives related to interoperability

Name of initiative / innovation	Relevant inputs
D-COM network	The D-COM network is led by Cardiff University and was formed to drive forward the adoption of the digitization of regulations, requirements and compliance checking systems in the built environment.
CEN/TC 442 - Building Information Modelling (BIM)	Standardization in the field of structured semantic life-cycle information for the built environment. The committee will develop a structured set of standards, specifications and reports which specify methodologies to define, describe, exchange, monitor, record

	and securely handle asset data, semantics and processes with links to geospatial and other external data. ¹⁵
<u>AIOTI (the Alliance for the Internet of Things Innovation) / WG3 semantic interoperability group</u>	AIOTI WG3 on standardization ¹⁶ . See for example some relevant documents/activities for this white paper: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “IoT standards and protocols landscape by AIOTI” at https://aioti.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/AIOTI-WG3-SDOs-Alliance-Landscape-IoT-LSP-standrad-framework-R2.9-Published.pdf • “Ontology landscape” by semantic interop task force of AIOTI WG3 (work in progress).
<u>BuildingSMART International Solution & Standards Program</u>	World-wide industry body developing open neutral standards to support open digital ways of working for the built asset industry. It is the owner and developer of the IFC Schema and its related ecosystem including digital data dictionary and use case management services
<u>Ready2services frame of reference</u>	In collaboration with the certifying body Certivéa, the SBA has established this label for Commercial Buildings. It is a baseline that sets out the requirements to be met by a Smart Building, an open and communicating building, ready for the services.
<u>Holochain</u>	Open-source framework that facilitates a peer-to-peer network. Can be used for developing diverse distributed apps

¹⁵ see ISO BIM standards ISO 16739, ISO 12006-3, ISO 23386

¹⁶ see description at https://aioti.eu/wg_standardisation/

4. Barriers and drivers

4.1. Barriers

Barriers to the market uptake of smart buildings related to interoperability of building components and systems were reviewed and prioritised by the Task Force. The top barriers are highlighted below.

VALUE CHAIN	Vendor Lock-in (e.g. in the case of solutions sold with support & maintenance)	<i>Top barriers according to the Task Force</i>
	Readiness of industrial players and complexity of value chain	
REGULATION	Lack of industrial standards for homogenous interoperability	
	Data integration issues related to GDPR	
	Lack of regulation preventing or discouraging vendor lock-in	
SOCIAL	User acceptance / Final users' awareness and user friendliness	
	Complex inclusiveness, lack of human-centric solutions for non-expert users	
ECONOMIC	Reluctancy to adopt interoperability by manufacturers as it might affect market share / profit	
	Reluctancy to adopt interoperability by service providers / integrators who generate a lot of business on tailor made integrations	
	Cost related to IoT investment or semantic modelling (i.e. BIM)	
TECHNICAL	Cybersecurity of open systems	
	Low "Smartness" of the building stock/ legacy equipment	

4.2. Drivers

The drivers identified by the Task Force are as illustrated below. The strongest driver is related to regulation and standards:

VALUE CHAIN	Market push	<i>Top drivers according to the Task Force</i>
	Initiatives from market actors providing energy and non-energy services	
	Democratisation of data assets/ strong push to make all the data available to all market players in the value chain	
REGULATION & STANDARDS	EU Regulation: EPBD, SRI, DIGITAL LOGBOOK and RENOVATION PASSPORT	
	Renovation Wave	
	(Open) standards	
SOCIAL	New trends in health care (tele-assistance)	
	Customers requesting more plug-&-play solutions, democratisation of smart devices	
	Buildings becoming active in energy market: occupants require interoperability	
	Inclusiveness: a building should be as simple as a smart phone	
ECONOMIC	Reduced development costs for new services thanks to interoperability	
TECHNICAL	Cybersecurity: push to have a more interoperable system providing increased shared resistance to cyberattacks	
	Enhancement of potential synergies among devices	
	Crowd-evaluation of protocols	

5. Gaps

Various activities required to overcome the barriers and leverage the drivers related to interoperability were suggested and prioritised by the Task Force members and are presented in Table 4. The priority ones according to the Task Force are in bold.

Table 4: Suggested R&I activities

Type of activity	Activities
R&I	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop a unified and shared EU ontology & semantics for devices, equipment and assets (e.g. “Dictionary” bringing together all relevant semantics and ontologies, with shared definitions) - Develop interoperable software tools allowing building operators to select their monitoring/actuation/analysis packages as a “kit of Parts” type approach – giving improved flexibility and performance for the specific use case of their building. - Develop Plug and play solutions specifically targeted at existing buildings. (hassle free, no need for architect, service integrator,...)
Demo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Build a marketplace for the manufacturing industry to respond to interoperability-related services - Set up exemplary projects showcasing the added value of interoperable equipment
Regulation & legal framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Set up a central registry to give users a personal unique interface for filling, updating and sharing (give access to) information, in a just and safe way. Possible interoperability considering EU/national norms and portals (ex. Digital ID card) ¹⁷ - Integrate interoperability into digital logbook / building passport - Develop regulations to demand open standards, create an imperative for strategic data flexibility - Set up minimum levels of interoperability/smartsness of buildings needed to monitor energy performance and maintain the energy certificates validation - Define open and modular end-to-end interoperability and data management frameworks that enable open standards-based communication along the demand response value chain
Certification & standardisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop an interoperability label (with cybersecurity certification) at device scale - Standardization of semantic data tags for linked data in buildings - Set up exemplary projects showcasing the added value of smart building certification assessing the level of interoperability (e.g. Ready2Service certification, Smart Score, WiredScore)
Scaling up & industrialisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop approaches to facilitate the uptake of smart and interoperable solutions: start with the safety/security equipment (e.g. fire alarms + extra installation related to security and cybersecurity) - Develop data processing agreements with different stakeholders - Implement naming and tagging on devices (not as a part of BIM or DT)

¹⁷ <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-area-of-justice-and-fundamental-rights/file-security-of-id-cards-and-residence-documents-of-eu-citizens>, <https://www.monica-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/Personal-DataProtection-for-IoT-Deployments-final-MI.pdf>, https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/12528-Systeme-d%E2%80%99identification-numerique-de-l%E2%80%99UE-pour-les-transactions-en-ligne-a-travers-l%E2%80%99Europe_fr

Upskilling & awareness raising	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Public acceptance/ awareness of interoperability: better educate or target the right market segment- Upskilling of practitioners in the field to fully take advantage of smart building and smart construction technologies
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6. Conclusion

This document formalises the collaborative work performed by the members of SmartBuilt4EU task force 2, on a voluntary basis, during the period March - June 2021. It also integrates the feedback collected during 1) a peer review conducted by VITO in June 2021, and 2) an open consultation process during in July – August 2021.

Based on an analysis of the state of the art and the identification of barriers and drivers, the main objective of this paper is to detect some Research and Innovation gaps that still need to be addressed in the coming years in order to improve the interoperability of smart building solutions and systems.

This White Paper will feed the elaboration of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda that the SmartBuilt4EU consortium will present to the European Commission.

Task Force 2 will investigate two more topics during 2021 – 2022: next topic, starting October 2021, will focus on **Optimised building costs**, i.e. integrating tools for optimised costs over the full life cycle (including BIM, digital twin, predictive maintenance, Artificial Intelligence, weather forecast, predictive control).

If you have some expertise to share on this topic, you are invited to join the task force and contribute to the next White Paper (contact detail below).

To receive the updates on the SmartBuil4EU task forces, White Papers and events, please register here:
<https://smartbuilt4eu.eu/join-our-community/>

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8. Annex 1: list of H2020 projects reviewed

Table 5: list of relevant EU projects

Project	Status	Weblink	Relevant inputs
Interoperability in buildings (BEMS, etc)			
BRESAER	completed	http://www.bresae.r.eu/	Multiple and diverse data sources integration for energy management systems
PHOENIX	Ongoing	https://eu-phoenix.eu/	Adapt-&Play (A&P) solutions to seamlessly integrate legacy equipment, smart appliances, smart controls and technology building systems. <i>See details in Annex 7.</i>
PLUG FOR HARVEST	Ongoing	https://www.plugin-harvest.eu/	Adaptative facade and device interoperability for building retrofiting
PRECEPT Less Energy > Smarter Buildings	Ongoing	https://www.precept-project.eu	Proactive and Predictive Building Management System (PP-BMS) based on devices/systems interoperability and innovative technologies such as digital twins, artificial intelligence, etc.
Interoperability with the grid (see also TF3)			
HOLISDER	completed (31.03.2021)	http://holisder.eu	Analysis of EU-wide interoperability standards and data models and harmonization requirements. CIM complying with OneM2M, SAREF, USEF, OpenADR, IEC-61850 and OpenADR 2.0b standards enriched with semantics related to human comfort profiles and demand elasticity
interconnect	ongoing	https://interconnectproject.eu	Connect existing platforms (without changing them, using directly their APIs) in homes, buildings, grids via a semantic interoperability layer that uses standardized ontologies (such as SAREF, but not limited to) for communication. See in particular Section 5 of deliverable D2.1 Secure interoperable IoT smart home/building and smart energy system reference architecture ¹⁸
TABEDE Towards buildings ready for Demand Response	completed	http://www.tabede.eu/	Demand response schemes thanks to a low cost extender for BMS systems or as standalone system
BIM interoperability & digital construction			
BIM SPEED	ongoing	https://www.bim-speed.eu/en	BIM-based interoperability, extended IFC data model

¹⁸ available at <https://interconnectproject.eu/resources/?active=public-deliverables>

	Ongoing	www.digiplaceproject.eu	DigiPLACE is a framework allowing the development of future digital platforms as common ecosystems of digital services that will support innovation, commerce, etc. It will define a Reference Architecture Framework for digital construction platform based on an EU-wide consensus involving a large community of stakeholders, resulting in a strategic roadmap for successful implementation of this architecture.
	Ongoing	https://www.bim4eeb-project.eu/	BIM4EEB develops a BIM-based toolset – BIMMS - which offers a set of functionalities that meet the stakeholders' needs during the renovation work. BIMMS can integrate tools and enable the data interoperability through data exchange services.
Big data and digital twins			
	ongoing	https://www.bigb-project.eu/	Building Information aGGregation, harmonization and analytics platform
	ongoing		BEYOND introduces a reference big data platform implementation for collecting, processing and analyzing building data, while transforming them into a tradeable commodity through the development of appropriate data sharing mechanisms for data sharing between different stakeholders.
	Ongoing	https://sphere-project.eu/	Digital Twins + ICT Systems of Systems infrastructure based on Platform as a Service (PaaS) service to allow large scale data, information and knowledge integration and synchronization
Smart City Projects			
	completed	https://espresso-project.eu	Although more related to Smart Cities, some concepts for interoperability and ways to reach interoperable solutions were introduced
	Ongoing	https://www.mysmartlife.eu/	Reference architecture for interoperable solutions in Smart Cities

9. Annex 2: Detailed project description

9.1. PHOENIX

PHOENIX objective for adapt-&-play seamless integration of legacy building equipment/systems:

PHOENIX aims to solve those problems by using Adapt-&-Play (A&P) solutions to seamlessly integrate legacy equipment, smart appliances, smart controls and technology building systems. These A&P solutions will allow the use of smart operation strategies for the upgraded equipment that should increase the satisfaction, health and well-being of all building's occupants. Furthermore, those upgraded appliances should allow the automatic realisation of demand response actions sent by aggregators or DSOs. Plug-&-Play plugs, smart meters, wired and wireless smart sensors, modification of HMI in large appliances and systems are some of the A&P solutions that PHOENIX will test in different systems and appliances to increase their smartness and also their connectivity with other equipment in the building. The change of paradigm described above, consists not only on the adoption of a given standard by a specific industry, but also on a transformation in the way people use and interact with buildings. Similar to other digital transformations (shopping, communication, and advertising) the transformation on the building sector will require a large deal of adaptation from those providing and maintaining the buildings, as well as those that ultimately use them. For the successful change in this direction, PHOENIX will develop strategies that will enable the transformation of buildings into smarter ones. This "Adapt & Play" integration will enable that the devices are upgraded to smart ones, so they can be connected to the PHOENIX Smartness Building Hub and be an active components of smart services.

Beyond the state-of-the-art in hardware integration, PHOENIX will upgrade a large number of legacy systems and appliances in existing buildings by using Adapt-&-Play solutions to integrate seamlessly legacy equipment and technology building systems. Diverse communication technologies (i.e. Modbus, KNX, Bacnet) will be used by PHOENIX, as the ones defined above, to connect the legacy systems and appliances with the PHOENIX hub. Furthermore, these communication technologies will allow connecting the building with EEB stakeholders and markets, which may create opportunities to provide new services to the building's occupants and the grid. The greatest novelty brought by PHOENIX in this area is the simultaneous deployment of state-of-the-art technologies and communications solutions in existing buildings to upgrade the smartness of all antique legacy systems and appliances. Therefore, PHOENIX allows the refurbishment of existing equipment, which results in the best low-carbon cost-effective solution to increase the smartness of existing buildings.

Beyond the State-of-the-Art in multi-systems interoperability, PHOENIX aims at creating an ICT-based hub that is highly versatile, modular, interoperable (based on semantic descriptions and open APIs). To achieve that, PHOENIX will develop automatic semantic labelling and an Interoperable Data Space for enabling the multi-systems data exchange with building systems and external data sources. To support building end-users in the process of integration of their legacy systems and appliances, PHOENIX proposes the development of smart applications to provide a map of possible upgrades from most cost-effective to less one, which will provide to the end-user the higher level information to decide the most convenient upgrade in each case. Human-Building-Interaction technologies will be used by PHOENIX to facilitate the communication of the building appliances and systems with the building's occupants and managers. These improvements in communication between the building's systems and the occupants may increase their acceptance and preference for a wider range of indoor conditions, which simultaneously increases both the energy efficiency of the building and the satisfaction of the occupants. The orchestration of all equipment and devices in the building will be done through a reference architecture proposed by PHOENIX. This reference architecture will

account the heterogeneity and multi-systems nature of the data relevant to smart buildings. The architecture will feature standards and protocols for both the synergic operation of all equipment in the building and the effective communication with other stakeholders. The modular and openness of the proposed architecture is going to make PHOENIX easily adoptable and used by various smart buildings administrators.

Integration Layer for Adapt-&-Play Seamless Interoperability: This integration layer provides the mechanisms for the remote control and data monitoring from different building equipment, systems and external data sources (i.e. weather predictions) with heterogeneous protocols and technologies. To integrate the legacy equipment, PHOENIX will develop and deploy multiples IoT Gateways and Smart Controllers to turn on/off and measure the consumption of non-digital devices as well as to translate legacy protocols (e.g. Modbus, Zigbee, etc) of digital equipment to standardized Internet protocol (e.g. IP, HTTP) in order to monitor and control their operations. Moreover, this layer will integrate management systems available in existing building as well as external data sources that represent free online sites and datasets that offer building data (e.g. Building Information Models), energy-related data (e.g. energy tariffs) and weather predictions from national or international organizations (e.g. Copernicus). To achieve a high interoperability, PHOENIX will develop this layer in WP3 based on the standard approach of IDS standard (Industrial Data Space) that defines multiples IDS Agents to support the communication with different industrial and IoT protocols (i.e. COAP, REST, MQTT, HTTP, etc.) and heterogeneous data formats (i.e. XML, JSON, JSON-LD etc.) for the seamless interactions with IoT gateways, building management systems (BMS) and external data sources. Moreover, a framework of SRI performance will be created as a repository of upgrading possibilities of legacy equipment to be connected and integrated for improving the smartness of existing building. This layer will homogenise the communications protocols and data formats to enable the easy link between the physical assets and the next layer of knowledge creation.